

Determination of 3-Mercaptopropionic, Mercaptosuccinic and *o*-Mercaptobenzoic Acid by Lead Tetraacetate

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IN an attempt to titrate β -carboxy mercaptans in aqueous solutions by oxidimetric procedures, several anomalies were seen. In each case there was always an excessive consumption to oxidant which varied from one titration of another in an unaccountable fashion. While many water soluble mercaptans are oxidized terminally to disulfides by iodine in aqueous potassium iodide, mercaptans which have a free β -carboxyl group are strongly inclined to further oxidation¹. In a separate procedure involving titration with phenylhydrosulfate, we have observed that the initial concentration of mercaptan is of primary importance in their determination and that there are some mercaptans which are very susceptible to over oxidation.

Three mercaptans mentioned in title, which exhibit a tendency to overoxidation, are estimated based upon the oxidation by excess lead tetraacetate in 60% acetic acid to corresponding sulfonic acids:

Consumptions are high (six equivalents), so that smaller amounts can be determined. The method is simple and suitable for the determination of purity of refined materials. The average error is below 0.5% for 2–50 mg of mercaptan samples.

Reagents

An approximately 0.05M lead tetraacetate solution was prepared by reacting Pb_3O_4 with glacial acetic acid². Its strength was determined iodometrically³. All the three mercaptan samples were gifted from Evans Chemetics, New York, U.S.A., to whom the authors are grateful. Solutions were prepared of 3-mercaptopropionic and mercaptosuccinic acid in distilled water and their strength was determined by titration with mercuric perchlorate⁴. In the case of *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid, the product was recrystallized from benzene to a constant melting point of 164°, and standard solutions were made by dissolving right amounts of it in glacial acetic acid.

Procedure

2–20 ml of sample solution containing 2–50 mg of mercaptan was pipetted into a 250 ml flask. A measured excess (50% suffices) of tetraacetate salt solution was added. Before adding tetraacetate, calculated volume of distilled water (or glacial acetic acid) was added so as to maintain the overall acetic acid concentration very near to 60% by volume.

The flask was left at about 27° for a period of 15 min in the case of 3-mercaptopropionic and mercaptosuccinic acid, and for 30 min when *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid was being determined. Residual lead tetraacetate was estimated by adding a solution of potassium iodide and sodium acetate (100:500 g in 1 l) and titrating the liberated iodine with 0.04N thiosulfate solution to starch end-point. A blank determination was carried in a similar manner to record the hydrolysis of tetraacetate salt.

Results

The recommended procedure appears to be an elegant oxidimetric method for the analysis of three mercaptans mentioned. Reactions are fairly fast in the medium taken; application of lower acetic acid concentration unduly hydrolyzes the tetraacetate salt, although the rate of oxidation increases with decreasing acetic acid concentration. On adding excess of oxidant (as high as four-fold) the results were unaffected. The present method may be applied to other mercaptan samples.

The proposed method has the advantage that the conditions are not critical, and that accurate results are readily achieved even with dilute solutions.

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Chemical Study of the Seeds of *Vitex negundo*, L.

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VITEX negundo, L. (Verbenaceae) is an important medicinal plant, and its roots and leaves are used as a tonic and in various ailments¹. The leaves of the drug have been mentioned to contain essential oil², gluconitol, hydroxyaromatic acids and a glucoside³. An alkaloid nishindine⁴, vitamin C, and carotene⁵, and 5-hydroxy, 3,6,7,3',4'-penta-methoxy-flavone⁶ have also been isolated from the leaves. In view of the importance of the drug and since almost no significant work appeared to have been carried out so far on the seeds of the plant, their chemical study was undertaken in these laboratories.

The dried and powdered seeds of the plant (5 Kg.) were subjected to solvent extraction with petroleum-ether (60°–80°), benzene and alcohol successively at their boiling points for 18 hr, and the different extracts were examined.

The petroleum-ether extract (90 g.) of the seeds of the plant, obtained after removal of the solvent, was neutral to litmus and gave positive Liebermann Burchard test. This extract was subjected to steam-distillation and then the residue was saponified in benzene with alcoholic KOH ($N/2$, 400 ml.) for 6 hr. The unsaponifiable matter (45 g.) was then divided into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble parts.

The acetone-insoluble part (1.25 g.) on chromatography (alumina), elution with petroleum-ether (60°–80°), and purification yielded a colourless product (A–350 mg), m.p. 66°. It appeared to be a paraffin; i.r. peaks at 2920, 2960 and 2850 cm^{-1} (C–H saturated); 1460, 1470 and 1375 cm^{-1} (C–CH₃); 720 and 730 cm^{-1} (CH₂)_n. Found: C, 85.0; H, 14.4%; calc. for C₃₀H₆₂: C, 85.22; H, 14.78%. But later Gas-liquid-chromatography showed it to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes (C₂₇–C₂₇) containing mainly *n*-trtriacontane (C₃₃, 36.8%); *n*-hentriacontane (C₃₁, 35%); *n*-penta-triacontane (C₃₅, 13.4%) and *n*-nonacosane (C₂₉, 7.2%). Odd numbered alkanes predominated as usual.

The acetone-soluble part (40 g.) of the petroleum-ether extract was also chromatographed over alumina. A product B (100 mg, TLC. homogeneous), m.p. 135°–36°, (α)_D²⁵ –32.5°, was obtained in shining flakes on elution with chloroform and crystallisation (methanol). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test, yellow colour with tetra-nitro-methane and was identified as β -sitosterol by mixed-melting-point determination, co-T.L.C. with authentic specimen of the compound, and preparation of its acetate (m.p. 122°) and benzoate (m.p. 144°–6°)⁷. The benzene-extract (25 g.) of the seeds on chromatography (alumina) and crystallisation (methanol) yielded only one pure compound which was identified as β -sitosterol in the above manner.

The alcoholic extract (100 g.) obtained from the defatted seeds (4 kg.) showed the presence of carboxylic acids, phenolic products and reducing sugars. Glucose was identified in the extract by descending co-paper chromatography (Whatman filter paper No. 1) with authentic specimen of the sugar using solvent system (organic layer) consisting of *n*-butanol : water : acetic acid (4 : 5 : 1, V/v, 36 hr) and aniline phthalate as spraying reagent.

The ethanolic extract after removal of the solvent was extracted with hot water. The hot-water-soluble part (residue) was then repeatedly extracted with aq. solution of sodium carbonate (10%). The alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was concentrated and the residue, after removal of ether was dissolved in hot water and then treated with lead acetate solution and the precipitate thus formed was filtered. The filtrate was delead (H₂S), concentrated and the residue was crystallised from hot water. It yielded *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid (m.p. 215°–16°) identified by mixed m.p. and co-ascending-paper-chromatography

with authentic specimen using solvent system *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5, V/v; organic layer) and ferric chloride as spraying reagent⁸.

The yellow precipitate was also decomposed by H₂S, concentrated, and the residue on crystallisation (hot water) gave another acid m.p. 287°, and identified as 5-oxy-isophthalic acid (m.p. 288°, lit)⁹.

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Analytical applications of *p* NN-Bis-2 Cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde in the detection of oils. Part I

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THE role of tertiary aminobenzaldehydes particularly *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (DAB) as analytical reagents is well known. *p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde has been used in the detection of urea^{1,2} and bile pigments in urine³. Lienodo⁴ has reported the determination of blood urea levels with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. Colour reaction of sesame oil with 2% solution of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid has been reported by Fleig⁵. Looking to the structural similarity of the *p* NN-bis-2-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde with DAB it was thought of interest to test this aldehyde for the detection of vegetable and animal oils. The aldehyde was prepared according to the method suggested by Thomas and Ittyerah⁶.